

tested were 50, 75, and 100 liters/ha applied by the low-volume sprayer (mist blower), and 500, 750, and 1000 liters/ha with each high-volume sprayer (hand-compression, foot, and knapsack). For convenience, the volumes were categorized as low, medium, and high. The fixed dose of the insecticide, fenitrothion as Sumithion 500 E at 1.0 kg a.i./ha mixed in varying water volumes, was applied by each sprayer on 11 October 1976 at the grain-formation stage of the variety Saken. The 12

treatments and control were replicated 3 times in a factorial randomized design. Insecticide was applied only once.

Equal and uniform application of the insecticidal fluid was ensured by adjustment of the operator's speed and timing. At spraying time the larvae were at the 4th- to 5th-instar stage. The performance of sprayers and the influence of water volumes were evaluated on the basis of larvae reduction.

The hand-compression spray equipment was significantly superior in reduction of larvae (95%) compared with the mist-blower (56%). The lever-operated knapsack sprayer and the foot sprayer performed equally well in pest control. Low water volume gave 83% control and medium volume, 83%. The high-volume treatment gave 68% larvae reduction. The average effect of treatment combinations was significantly higher than that of the control. ■

Effectiveness of foliar spray insecticides in brown planthopper control in Thailand

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Six insecticides were tested in the 1977 dry season in central Thailand. The experiment was in a randomized complete

block design with 7 treatments and 4 replications. The 5- x 6-m² plots were planted to the variety RD1. Insecticides were applied by knapsack sprayers at a concentration of 0.1% active ingredient at 40, 50, and 70 days after transplanting. Brown planthopper (BPH) populations were collected by a D-vac suction machine 1 day before and 1 day after spraying.

BPH populations after the first

insecticide application differed significantly between treatments (see table). The most effective insecticides were carbofuran, MIPC, MTMC, BPMC, monocrotophos, and carbaryl. Results of the second and third applications were similar to those of the first.

Carbofuran gave the highest grain yield, followed by monocrotophos. Carbaryl gave lower yields than MIPC, MTMC, or BPMC. ■

Effectiveness of insecticides applied as foliar sprays against the brown planthopper (BPH) in central Thailand, 1977.

Treatment ^a	Formulation	BPH population ^b						Yield (t/ha)
		1st application (40DT)		2nd application (50DT)		3d application (70DT)		
		DBT	DAT	DBT	DAT	DBT	DAT	
Carbofuran	2F	1,271 a	15 a	144 a	19 a	149 ab	3 a	1.7 a
MIPC	50 WP	1,155 a	43 a	579 b	52 a	89 a	1 a	0.9 bc
MTMC	50 WP	1,875 bc	38 a	51 a	21 a	94 a	1 a	1.1 b
BPMC	50 WP	1,595 b	16 a	142 a	26 a	108 a	2 a	1.0 b
Monocrotophos	56 WSC	1,365 ab	413 b	195 b	185 b	214 bc	5 ab	1.3 ab
Carbaryl	85 WP	1,909 c	41 a	336 b	217 b	374 c	13 b	0.7 c
Control	-	2,184 d	1,215 c	751 b	1,229 c	417 c	154 c	0.2 d

^aApplied at 0.1% concentration.

^bAdults and nymphs from 4 replications.

DT = days after transplanting, DBT = days before treatment, DAT = days after treatment.

Means in a column followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Soil and crop management

An easy mass-multiplication method for blue-green algae

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Commendable field experiments on the use of blue-green algae (equal to 25–30 kg N/ha) for higher rice yields have been conducted in various agroclimatic regions of India. Once the

yield-increasing effects of algal inoculation are better recognized, large-scale production of algal inoculum becomes important — at least in areas with favorable conditions. Until now, algae have been multiplied in concrete tanks or metal troughs, which require high initial expenditures that marginal farmers cannot afford.

Because the merit of such a device lies in the farmers' adoption of methods of preparing their own inoculum, experiments were conducted at the Paddy Experiment Station, Aduthurai, to develop a suitable multiplication technique. In 1978 a simple and easy method for mass multiplication of blue-green algae was standardized by